

Electronic information: new opportunities for rice scientists

I. Wallace, Information Center, IRRI

DR. ORYZA'S DILEMMA

Dr. Oryza, chief scientist of the National Rice Institute, is in a dilemma. The Global Bank is after him again for a report about how the special grant of \$25,000 had been spent. The money was to have paid for attendance at international conferences by senior research staff. But not a single dollar has been spent and the financial year is drawing to a close. Of course, the last thing he wants is to return the grant unspent, but he has no idea about upcoming conferences and meetings, and by the time announcements of such meetings usually reach him, the conference is often already over.

In addition, the International Subscriptions Agency has just sent him a bill for next year's subscriptions to five international journals and his tiny operating budget would be slashed again. He has no recourse but to cut these last few international subscriptions and rely on national

journals only. He would surely incur the wrath of his fellow scientists who would be bitterly angered by this cutback in subscriptions.

To top it all, Dr. Sativa, the fiercest critic of the Institute library which Dr. Oryza also manages, has been complaining about the lack of information resources in the library, which makes it problematic for him to work on collaborative projects with other national program scientists in other countries. Dr. Oryza would just have to see what could be done about strengthening the library.

Many scientists in the national programs have this common problem: lack of ready access to current scientific information. What can be done about it? This review enumerates the various options available to national program scientists who have access to the Internet.

Scientists are now offered a vast array of new, electronic possibilities, most of which fall under the general heading of ICTs (information and communication technologies). Basically, what this means is that information is increasingly being packaged in new electronic formats that make storage, retrieval, and transfer far easier than in the case of paper. Some say that the arrival of these ICTs is the most important advance in information dissemination since the invention of the printing press more than five centuries earlier. Let's review some of the exciting new options now available to scientists, starting with libraries.

Virtual libraries

Libraries are gradually being transformed from quasi-warehouses of books and journals, where the emphasis was on *ownership* of information, to electronic clearinghouses that focus on *access* to information. It is important to note that these new "virtual libraries" have not abandoned information in the traditional formats. Books and journals will not disappear overnight,¹ in fact, they will endure for a long time to come. Nonetheless, they are being supplemented by online, electronic resources, which are not "acquired" in the traditional sense. Instead, computer links are established to these electronic resources, making them locally available, even when the host computer site may be located on the other side of the planet.

In 1996, the IRRI Library launched its Web site² and, for the first time, users could consult many of the resources of the Library without having to travel to Los Baños. Formerly, to use the card catalogue, users would have to actually be physically present in the library building. For access, this change is nothing short of revolutionary and the Library is now regularly "visited" by clients based in such far-away countries as Cuba, India, and Mozambique. Distance, always a barrier to information access, has thus been at least partially eliminated.

New computer technology has brought many other advantages to the library world. For example, complicated literature searches are now far easier to perform. Consider this hypothetical library search:

Subject:	weed control in rice
Exclusion:	chemical herbicides
Dates:	1995 onwards
Languages:	English or Japanese
Type of document:	books only

Such a search would take a long time in a traditional card catalogue but can be performed in seconds in an electronic catalogue, even in one located thousands of kilometers away. Furthermore, references can be saved for later use or even sent to an e-mail address. Thus, scientists are no longer obliged to write down references of interest; they can be saved electronically, even several hundred at a time.

¹At an international conference in Singapore, in March 1998, Brian Land, director of the British Library, stated that "if the book were to be invented today, it would be proclaimed as a marvel of ingenuity and practicality." ²<http://ricelib.irri.cgiar.org>

Today, there are more than 6,000 electronic libraries accessible from scientists' computers, and most of these are accessible through a central Internet-based service, WebCats,³ which is maintained in Canada. Users can connect to WebCats and then search for libraries by country/city or by type of library, e.g., "special" or "university." Libraries offering electronic access include the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology,⁴ the University of Tsukuba (Japan),⁵ the National Library of Malaysia,⁶ and the University of Chiang Mai,⁷ in Thailand. Not surprisingly, most electronic libraries are in developed countries. Three good agricultural libraries are the University of Queensland,⁸ in Australia, the Wageningen Agricultural University,⁹ in the Netherlands, and OhioLink,¹⁰ in the United States, which is a consortium of 18 large libraries, including that of Ohio State University. Anyone with an Internet connection can "visit" these libraries and see what has been published recently about rice or other subjects.

Electronic journals

As the century ends, a revolution is taking place in journal publishing: more and more journals are appearing in electronic format.¹¹ These e-journals, as they are known, have several advantages over traditional paper journals: (1) production costs are very low, there being no significant paper or delivery expenses; (2) they are available almost instantly through the Internet, whereas, with print journals, subscribers have to wait for delivery in the mail; (3) text and figures can be modified or augmented at any time; (4) content is electronically searchable—even many years' issues in a single search; and (5) issues do not need to be bound or shelved, nor are they ever lost or mutilated. Undoubtedly, e-journals will become increasingly important in the coming years.

How does one access an e-journal? In the case of commercial journals, a fee of one kind or another must be paid before access is possible and, usually, this fee is about the same as the cost of a print subscription, except in the case of pay per view (PPV), where a smaller amount is paid to read a single article or journal issue. Of course, most scientists would prefer free access and this may indeed come to pass, but probably not very soon. Virtually all of the major scientific journals now offer electronic access.

Many noncommercial journals are also available through the Internet and access is free. Increasingly, libraries such as IRRU's offer their readers a selection of online journals, in addition to their traditional print subscriptions. Listed below are a few examples of noncommercial e-journals of possible interest to rice scientists:

*Electronic Journal of Biotechnology*¹²
*Farm Journal Today*¹³
*Food Outlook*¹⁴
*Integrated Crop Management*¹⁵
*International Rice Research Notes*¹⁶
*New Agriculturalist*¹⁷
*Rice Journal*¹⁸
*Weeds World*¹⁹

The advantages of e-journals are so many that, increasingly, scientists will be reading them on a computer screen, rather than awaiting the arrival of a paper journal from New York, Amsterdam, or Bangkok.

E-journals also offer new possibilities to scientists, many of who are unable to publish in traditional journals because of high page charges and a preference by some of the leading journals for established authors from advanced countries. With the arrival of e-journals, the old power structure may find its hold on scientific publishing somewhat weakened if only because unpublished scientists now have new alternatives. They can publish their articles in an e-journal or even start one of their own! Given the very low cost of electronic publishing, launching a new journal is not such a daunting task as it would have been a few years ago.

Meanwhile, major newspapers have also taken the plunge and are offering free electronic access to their readers. Some popular Asian titles are:

Bangladesh	<i>The Daily Star</i> ²⁰
China	<i>South China Morning Post</i> ²¹
India	<i>The Times of India</i> ²²
Korea	<i>Korea Times</i> ²³
Philippines	<i>Manila Bulletin</i> ²⁴
Vietnam	<i>Saigon Times Daily</i> ²⁵
Thailand	<i>Bangkok Post</i> ²⁶

³<http://www.lights.com/webcats> ⁴<http://library.ust.hk> ⁵<http://www.tulips.tsukuba.ac.jp/welcome.english.html> ⁶<http://www.infomal.com.my/library/virtua/index.html> ⁷<http://www.cmu.ac.th> ⁸<http://www.library.uq.edu.au/iad/mainmenu.html> ⁹<http://www.agralin.nl/desktop> ¹⁰<http://olcl.ohiolink.edu> ¹¹A good overview of electronic journals and their future is provided by Thomas J. Walker, "The future of scientific journals: free access or pay for view?," *American Entomologist*, Fall 1998, p. 135-138. A much longer Web-published article by the same author features illustrations and abundant hyperlinks to relevant literature and examples. Titled "The electronic future of scientific journals," this article can be viewed at the following Web address: <http://cssr.vr.entnem.ufl.edu/~walker/fewww/aedraft.htm> ¹²<http://www.ejb.org> ¹³<http://www.farmjournal.com> ¹⁴<http://www.fao.org/waicent/faoinfo/economic/giews/english/fo/fotoc.htm> ¹⁵<http://www.ipm.iastate.edu/ipm/icm> ¹⁶<http://www.cgiar.org/irri/irrn.htm> ¹⁷<http://www.new-agri.co.uk> ¹⁸<http://www.ricejournal.com> ¹⁹<http://nasc.nott.ac.uk:8300/home.html> ²⁰<http://www.dailystarnews.com> ²¹<http://www.scmp.com> ²²<http://www.timesofindia.com> ²³<http://www.koreatimes.co.kr> ²⁴<http://www.mb.com.ph> ²⁵<http://www.saigon-news.com> ²⁶<http://www.bangkokpost.net>

Similarly, newspapers published in other parts of the world are also available on the World Wide Web.

Electronic document delivery

One difficulty faced by most scientists in developing countries is how to obtain print copies of journal articles that cannot be found online or where electronic access to them is expensive. This is no longer so daunting an undertaking as before and libraries such as IRRI's offer fast and inexpensive document delivery services to their clients. Under optimum conditions, a scientist could easily receive a copy of a requested article in less than an hour, even if she or he happened to live thousands of kilometers away from the IRRI Library. Here is an example of how this works:

1. A scientist in New Delhi searches IRRI's online Rice Bibliography,²⁷ selects references of interest, and sends them to her local e-mail account
2. The scientist then sends the saved references back to the IRRI Library by e-mail²⁸
3. The IRRI Library sends the complete article to the scientist in New Delhi, using Ariel software

A new software package designed to deliver short texts over the Internet, Ariel²⁹ works quickly and inexpensively. Text transmitted by Ariel is very clear and, of course, there are no fax or mail charges. Best of all, texts can be sent in a few seconds, either across the street or to the other side of the world, to anyone with an Internet connection. Once again, distance is becoming less of an obstacle to fast access to information.

The IRRI Library will provide copies of articles about rice, but what about other subjects? Here, too, there are some good electronic possibilities. One of the most interesting is UnCover,³⁰ which stands out in what is becoming a very competitive field.³¹ UnCover is based in the United States and offers online access to the tables of contents of more than 17,000 journals covering most subject areas. Anyone can connect to UnCover and search by author, subject, journal title, and so on. Thus, a search by author would retrieve articles written by a particular author and published in one or more journals. Users can search for as long as they like with no charges being imposed by UnCover. Obviously, this is quite advantageous for scientists, but, not unsurprisingly, UnCover needs to make money and it does this mainly through its document delivery service. Here is how it works. After a user has identified articles of interest, these are marked for overnight delivery by fax. Costs are quite high, unfortunately, usually more than \$15 for a single article, but the service is quick and easy to use, not to mention far less expensive than subscribing to costly journals. A companion service, UnCover Reveal, will send to any

e-mail address the tables of contents of up to 50 journals, as they are published, for an annual charge of only \$25.

Although very popular with some users, commercial services such as UnCover are usually too expensive for scientists in developing countries where, in any case, more affordable local alternatives are often available. A good example is the Indian National Scientific Documentation Service (INSDOC),³² which routinely provides photocopies of articles from Indian journals. An equivalent service in China is offered by the National Library of China,³³ while in Pakistan, inquiries should be addressed to the National Agricultural Research Centre in Islamabad.³⁴ Many other Asian countries offer similar services, although electronic access is not always available.

Electronic bibliographic databases

In earlier times, scientists looking for articles on a particular subject usually had to wade through stacks of journals or abstract bulletins. Happily, this time-consuming task is now mostly in the past, thanks to electronic bibliographic databases such as IRRI's Rice Bibliography, a file containing about 180,000 references on rice and fully searchable online. Larger, more general agricultural databases can also be searched electronically, e.g., AGRICOLA, which is produced by the U.S. National Agricultural Library and is freely available on the Web.³⁵

Two other electronic databases also provide good coverage of agriculture: AGRIS, produced by FAO, and CAB Abstracts, from CAB International in the United Kingdom. Both are available on CD-ROM from SilverPlatter Information, Inc.³⁶ and on other platforms as well by arrangement with each vendor. At the IRRI Library, for example, AGRICOLA, AGRIS, and CAB Abstracts are all mounted in CD-ROM towers that provide instant network access to these databases to about 900 networked computers at the Institute. IRRI scientists can thus search these vast files without even having to leave their office or laboratory, 24 hours a day if need be.

Meanwhile, a popular option with scientists these days is to set up their own electronic databases with a product such as ProCite.³⁷ With this software, scientists can build up personal bibliographies by either typing in references themselves or by electronically importing them from other databases, such as the IRRI Rice Bibliography or CAB Abstracts. This is an ideal way to keep track of office reprint collections.

Other electronic possibilities

Almost limitless amounts of electronic information can now be accessed by anyone with an Internet connection. Examples are:

²⁷<http://ricelib.irri.cgiar.org> ²⁸E-mail address: c.austria@cgiar.org ²⁹For more information about Ariel, visit this Web site: <http://www.rlg.org/ariel.html> ³⁰Web address: <http://uncweb.carl.org> ³¹The Document Solution is another well-known service. It is offered by the publishers of *Current Contents* and the Web address is <http://ids.isinet.com> ³²Contact Mrs. Alicja Shrivastava. E-mail: mcs@sirnetd.ernet.in ³³Contact Mrs. Wu Jingsheng. E-mail: dcjyb@public.nlc.gov.cn ³⁴Contact Shahnaz Zuberi, Sr. Information Officer, NARC. E-mail: SIU@DSI-NARC.sdnpk.undp.org ³⁵<http://www.nal.usda.gov/ag98> ³⁶<http://www.silverplatter.com> ³⁷<http://www.risinc.com>

Institutes, organizations, universities. Most of these now have their own Web sites that offer visitors vast amounts of information about personnel, programs, services, and the like. A selected list is available at the IRRI Library Web site and includes one such as CAB International,³⁸ FAO,³⁹ IRRI,⁴⁰ the M.S. Swaminathan Research Foundation,⁴¹ and the Chinese Agricultural University.⁴²

Meteorological information. Is it hot or cool in Kathmandu? Will it rain in Nairobi? CNN⁴³ and other organizations have the answers at their Web sites.

Cultural visits. More and more museums are establishing electronic sites and IRRI's Riceworld Museum and Learning Center is one of them.⁴⁴ A related Web site, known as Riceweb,⁴⁵ links visitors to dozens of rice-related sites worldwide.

Books and publishing. A phenomenon of the late 1990s is the electronic bookstore, which offers customers a huge selection of books at very competitive prices. Thus, a rice scientist in Hyderabad or Jakarta can now buy the latest books without leaving home. Two well-established e-bookstores are Amazon⁴⁶ in the United States and Waterstones⁴⁷ in the United Kingdom. Similarly, all the major international publishers have now posted their complete catalogues on the Web.

Reference information. Virtually any subject can now be explored on the Internet, from airline timetables to software products. Many universities have assembled on their Web sites wide-

ranging selections of electronic reference information, and one of the best is offered by Purdue University⁴⁸ in the United States.

Web sites with an agricultural focus. There are many of these and a small selection can be found at the IRRI Library Web site, such as AgBioForum,⁴⁹ AgriNet,⁵⁰ and Agronomic Links across the Globe.⁵¹ These handy sites are open 24 hours a day and are free to users.

The importance of information

"Without information, there can be no development." This adage has been around for decades and it is as true today as it has ever been. Rice scientists understand all too well the importance of information as no research project can go very far without the appropriate facts and figures. Experimental data are vital in the research process, whether they come from the scientist's own field and laboratory investigations or whether they appear in journals, reports, and books.

Until very recently, however, information has often been difficult to acquire, especially for scientists in developing countries where really good science libraries are few and far between. We have seen, though, that new electronic technologies are changing the world fast and scientists who formerly suffered from a paucity of information may soon be complaining of "information overload!" This can only bode well for rice research in developing countries.

³⁸<http://www.cabi.org> ³⁹<http://www.fao.org> ⁴⁰<http://www.cgiar.org/irri> ⁴¹<http://www.mssrf.org> ⁴²<http://www.cau.edu.cn> ⁴³<http://www.cnn.com/WEATHER> ⁴⁴<http://www.riceworld.org> ⁴⁵<http://www.riceweb.org> ⁴⁶<http://www.amazon.com> ⁴⁷<http://www.waterstones.co.uk> ⁴⁸<http://thorplus.lib.purdue.edu/reference/index.html> ⁴⁹<http://www.agbioforum.missouri.edu> ⁵⁰<http://agrinet.tamu.edu> ⁵¹<http://www.agry.purdue.edu/agronomy/links>

About IRRI's Library and Documentation Service

Did you know...

- ...that IRRI has the world's biggest rice library?
- ...that it provides a free photocopy service¹ to rice scientist everywhere?
- ...that its catalogue and rice bibliography are available on the World Wide Web for searching, 24 hours a day²?
- ...that IRRI Library staff are waiting right now to receive your requests³?

We hope to be of service to you soon!

¹Maximum of 50 pages per request
²Web address: <http://ricelib.irri.cgiar.org>
³Write to Carmelita Austria at this address:
Library and Documentation Service,
International Rice Research Institute,
MCPO Box 3127, Makati City 1271, Philippines.
E-mail address: c.austria@cgiar.org